

Panagia tou Araka

also known as "Lagoudera"

By Ethan Schmidt, Simon Fraser University

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Panagia tou Araka is a Byzantine church of indeterminate date in the vicinity of the village of Lagoudera on the flanks of Madari in the Troodos Mountains of Cyprus, which may have been the katholikon of a monastery or else a private chapel. It is possessed of an unusually masterful and complete cycle of religious frescos dating to the year 1192. These were commissioned by a certain Leontios Authentes (perhaps a local notable), and painted by a certain Theodoros Apsevdis, an artist assumed by scholars to have come from Constantinople based on stylistic analysis. The frescos depict a variety of holy personages and biblical scenes, most famously an impressive and yet profoundly humanizing image of the Pantokrator on the interior of the dome, a painting of the Theotokos standing before her heavenly throne, seeming to offer up the infant Jesus to his eventual fate while flanked by angels bearing the instruments of the passion (associated by certain scholars with the an atmosphere of fatalism provoked by the tumultuous history of Cyprus under Isaakios Komnenos and later under crusader occupation), and a scene of the infant Christ being cradled by Saint Simeon while John the Baptist gestures towards them holding a scroll. All the paintings, executed with a mixture of costly materials including ultramarine, vermilion, and gold and silver leaf, exhibit a style characterized by dynamic movement, the use of sinuous line and brilliant color, and by an elegant attenuation of the figures reminiscent of contemporary fresco programs in North Macedonia such as at the Church of Saint Panteleimon at Gorno Nerezi or the Church of Saint George at Kurbinovo. Like the mural cycles at the aforementioned churches in the Thracian provinces, the frescos at Panagia tou Araka display the increasing humanism of Komnenian and Angelid art, with a certain focus on physical naturalism and profound emotion, as well as the inclusion of quotidian features of dress and landscape (such as the buildings in the background of the scene of the Presentation of the Virgin or the dress of the herdsmen in the scene of the Nativity), which may reflect the material realities of Twelfth Century Byzantium. Certain parts of the decorative cycle were restored following damage in the 14th century by a certain Deacon Leontios, while, in the 20th century, large scale cleaning, restoration, and analysis was conducted under the auspices of the Dumbarton Oaks Research Center and Collection. Included within the UNESCO designation of the 'Painted Churches of the Troodos Region', it remains a premier example of Byzantine painting both on the island of Cyprus and within the former territories of the Byzantine Empire.

Date Range: 1100 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Panagia tou Araka

Region tags: Cyprus

The Church of Panagia Tou Araka in Lagoudera on Cyprus

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Source 1: Winfield, David C., and Cyril Mango. "The Church of the Panagia Tou Arakos, Lagoudera: First Preliminary Report, 1968." *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 23/24 (1969)
- Source 2: Winfield, David., and Winfield, June. 2003. *The Church of the Panaghia Tou Arakos at Lagoudhera, Cyprus: the Paintings and Their Painterly Significance* / David and June Winfield. Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection.
- Source 3: Milliner, Matthew J. 2022. *Mother of the Lamb*. Minneapolis, Minnesota: Fortress Press.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://modelier.us.aldryn.io/models/c0e1725d-f6a8-49e5-a99f-8ec327012569/v2/embed/>
Notes: 3D Model of the Interior of the Church

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Notes: It has not been excavated but cleaned and restored scientifically under the auspices of Dumbarton Oaks.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Mountain

– Other [specify]: Araka is a local word for a wild variety of vetch that grows in the area

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Plantings

Notes: The ground seems to have been leveled and there are what appear to be a grove of olive trees in the vicinity.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Notes: It is situated somewhat outside the village of Lagoudera, suggesting that it belonged either to a private aristocratic mansion or to a monastery.

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: It has an apse at the end but is otherwise rectangular with a central dome.

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

Notes: There are olive trees in the vicinity.

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– I don't know

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It probably once belonged to a larger complex, though the nature of the site is unclear.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: It is unclear whether worship here would have been communal or relatively private, as it is unclear the exact identity and function of the church.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The restorations conducted did not significantly alter either the frescos or the fabric of the building.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The Theotokos

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Christ

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: The architecture and quality of the paintings suggest professional craftspeople.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Leontios Authentes was the sponsor of the paintings, and seems to have been a local notable.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Paints

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: There are numerous examples of floral and vegetal detailing typical of Byzantine art of the period.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: There are several dedicatory inscriptions.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures

project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Notes: Uncial dedicatory texts and labeling of saints.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other type of decoration:
– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
– Yes
Notes: The figures have eyes.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
– Yes
Notes: Christ, Angels

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife
– Yes

Notes: Anastasis Scene

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: There are images of the cross and the instruments of the passion, etc.

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Saints, Martyrs, and other religious figures.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: N/A

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably prayers were offered in the usual manner.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably prayers were offered to saints and angels as well as God or Christ themselves.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the

group.

– I don't know

Notes: Presumably it originally had priests and other functionaries assigned to it, but I do not believe it is permanently staffed as of today.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– I don't know

Notes: I presume that the local government of Cyprus is responsible for its maintenance.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably it once had lands and revenues attached to it, though in what capacity is unclear.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to ascertain the relationship of the church to the local community without knowledge of its exact purpose in the medieval period.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Panagia tou Araka, Winfield, David. "The Church of Panagia Tou Arakos, Lagoudera: First Preliminary Report", 1969. p.377-380

Reference: Panagia tou Araka, Milliner, Matthew. *Mother of the Lamb: The Story of a Global Icon*. Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2022.

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